

Unfolding the Universe: First Images and Spectra from the *James Webb Space Telescope*

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The National Aeronautics and Space Administration/European Space Agency/Canadian Space Agency (NASA/ESA/CSA) *James Webb Space Telescope* launched on 25 December 2021. After investing \$10 billion USD and two decades of construction and testing, all eyes were on the mission to see what it would reveal about the cosmos. The Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI) in Baltimore, Maryland, serves as *Webb's* mission and science operations centre. As part of that role, STScI's Office of Public Outreach leads the public engagement efforts for the mission, which includes preparing news releases. This article describes the multi-disciplinary efforts by STScI that went into developing and disseminating *Webb's* first images and spectra.

Introduction

The *James Webb Space Telescope* is the largest, most complex observatory sent into space. An infrared-wavelength observatory, *Webb's* key components include an enormous 6.5-meter primary mirror to collect infrared light, a supersized sun shield to keep the telescope cold, and four scientific instruments (Near-Infrared Camera, Near-Infrared Spectrograph, Near-Infrared Imager and Slitless Spectrograph, and Mid-Infrared Instrument) to conduct its ambitious science operations.

Webb examines every phase of cosmic history: from the first luminous glows after the Big Bang to the formation of galaxies, stars, and planets to the evolution of our own solar system.

On 11 and 12 July 2022, the first images captured by the long-awaited *James Webb Space Telescope* were revealed to the world. Six months after launch – and over 30 years since it was first conceived – *Webb* had just completed its final commissioning phase and was ready to begin official science operations.

The impact was immediate and overwhelming. *Webb's* observations adorned newspapers, screens, concert projections, and electronic billboards worldwide. Within a few days, more than 26,000 articles had appeared in media outlets.

This dramatic success was the culmination of years of preparation followed by weeks of nonstop production. A comprehensive communications effort reached well beyond text, imagery, and graphics to include social media, websites and

accessibility, international coordination, and community events.

This article highlights key aspects of the planning for *Webb*'s first images and spectra, as well as challenges and some lessons learned. It focuses on STScI's role in a broader effort led by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and its partners. While missions of *Webb*'s scale are infrequent, much of what is discussed here can be applied to other situations with challenges like multiple stakeholders (e.g., *Christensen et al., 2019*) or short timescales.

Images and Spectra

More than five years before launch, a committee was formed to select potential targets for *Webb*'s First Images. It was composed of representatives from NASA, the European Space Agency (ESA), the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), and the Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI) and considered a variety of selection criteria.

The final collection of images not only had to be beautiful in terms of tonality, contrast, composition, and colour balance, among other considerations (*Christensen et al., 2014*), but also needed to represent *Webb*'s four science themes (*Webb Space Telescope, n.d.a*), demonstrate its four instruments (*Webb Space Telescope, n.d.b*) and display that *Webb* was fully functional. Targets also needed to span a variety of visibility windows to accommodate any launch date, as *Webb*'s field of regard¹ only allows it to view about half of the sky at any particular time. The committee considered but ultimately avoided iconic *Hubble Space Telescope* targets like the Pillars of Creation (M16), wanting *Webb*'s first images to stand on their own. The complementary nature of *Webb* and *Hubble* would be explored later as scientific results began to accrue.

Based on *Webb*'s launch date and the expected length of commissioning (six months), nine targets were selected for observation: two each for star birth, star death and galaxies, one deep field, one exoplanet, and one backup star field. The first eight objects listed could demonstrate all modes and scientific themes of the observatory. It was decided that the "formation of stars and planets" science

theme would be doubly represented by stellar birth and death due solely to the previously observed beauty of these types of objects. The star field was chosen only as a backup to present the technical abilities of the multi-object spectroscopic array (MSA). Where multiple options for target types existed, a final choice would be made during production to ensure that the First Images represented the best of *Webb*'s capabilities regarding resolution, wavelength coverage, and sensitivity.

While images typically catch public attention, about 70% of *Webb*'s first year of science would involve spectroscopy. As a result, spectra would need to be part of the first public press release, both to put *Webb*'s capabilities on full display and to begin to help inform the public about the science that spectra would enable.

About a year before the *Webb* observations arrived, STScI formed a working group of outreach scientists, graphics designers and science communicators to develop a signature *Webb* style for presenting spectra. They reviewed a variety of example graphics to develop our internal best practices for communicating spectra with the public.

A guiding principle for *Webb* spectral graphics is that they should tell a clear story and not try to convey multiple information elements. The title section lists the target name, as well as what key message the graphic conveys (for example, "atmosphere composition" or "molecules in protoplanetary disk"). Chart axes are clearly labelled, and when the units of measurement are complex, they are removed in favour of broad descriptions. For example, rather than giving numerical flux values, the y-axis might be labelled "brighter" at the top and "dimmer" at the bottom.

These and other internally developed best practices (such as labelling protocols for elements and molecules) are still applied to spectra released as part of *Webb* news packages.

Production Process

Just after launch, a 31-member production team of scientists, instrument experts, media specialists, image processors, graphics designers, and science writers was formed at STScI to produce the first release. All team members signed non-disclosure agreements to keep the targets

confidential. This zone of confidentiality extended to only a handful of reviewers and leadership outside of the core team. This was an unusual step taken as a preventive measure at the request of mission leadership. The core team was also known as the ERO (early release observations) team, as they were responsible for the first public observations from *Webb* (*Pontoppidan et al. 2022*).

A detailed and intense production schedule was created based on when the various instrument modes would be commissioned and the windows of visibility for selected targets (Figure 1). The production schedule was just over six weeks long, from the first data received to the final publication in mid-July. In addition to coordinating timing, the schedule also helped ensure that no individual person was double-booked or expected to be working on two different products simultaneously.

NASA wanted to accelerate the first *Webb* release, pushing it up by two weeks or more into late June. The detailed production schedule, based on the commissioning timeline and target visibility windows, was used to demonstrate that it would be impossible to deliver a package in June that would achieve the project's overarching goal.

An essential production element was near-daily team meetings to review the latest status and progress of observations and products (Figure 2). This helped ensure that all production staff had the information they needed to make rapid progress and that the team could re-prioritise, reschedule, or pivot as needed.

In addition to the production staff, media representatives occasionally attended meetings. Several outlets proactively contacted STScI, requesting to cover the production process, primarily documentary filmmakers. NASA agreed to honour all of these requests equally as long as strict confidentiality was maintained and stories would not be published until after the 12 July release date. It was decided not to issue a formal media advisory or open invitation to minimise disruptive visits and allow the team to focus on production needs. (For another example of such behind-the-scenes access, see *Ikuta, 2022*).

Figure 1: An early version of the schedule used to track the development of all data-based assets (images, etc.) for the press release package of Webb’s First Images and spectra. Image Credit: STScI

Figure 2: An example of the daily production meetings that allowed an interdisciplinary team of scientists, instrument experts, and outreach staff to collaborate on the EROs. Image Credit: STScI

While most of the observations were relatively straightforward (one pointing of Webb’s NIRCam or MIRI instruments to take an image of a target), some proved to be more challenging. When the exoplanet target was observed, analysis quickly revealed that the data was contaminated by light from a second background star. As a result, a clean spectrum could not be obtained. The team pivoted to an alternate target observed just a few days later and yielded the desired spectrum of a hot Jupiter with clear signs of water vapour (Figure 3).

Another challenge involved obtaining spectra of galaxies within Webb’s First Deep Field. The NIRSpect (Near-Infrared Spectrograph) MSA microshutters are just 0.2 arcseconds wide, so proper calibration was essential. It was one of the last instrument modes to be commissioned, so the team did not get their observations until the evening of 29 to 30 June, leaving just a few days to process the data. The extra time before the instrument was ready allowed the scientists to use Webb’s NIRCam imaging to select particularly intriguing targets within the field for this

HOT GAS GIANT EXOPLANET WASP-96 b ATMOSPHERE COMPOSITION

NIRISS | Single-Object Slitless Spectroscopy

Figure 3: A spectrum of exoplanet WASP-96 b that was part of the early release observations. Image Credit: NASA, ESA, CSA, STScI

mode, resulting in *Webb*'s first spectra of high-redshift galaxies.

Press Release Text

Months before *Webb*'s launch, an understanding was reached among NASA, ESA, CSA, and STScI that the first news package would consist of a single, overarching press release with graphic assets (images and spectra) and associated captions.

A key strategy for developing image captions was to complete as much work as possible in advance. As a result, STScI employed a sequential, double-review process. Since the targets were known to the production team and select NASA reviewers, general captions with background information were written and sent through NASA review for each object. Once processed *Webb* data was in hand,

additional information was added to each caption and reviewed again. In cases where a selection was made between two targets, only the chosen one went through a second review. The remainder were saved for future image releases.

To streamline the process, the review teams at the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center and NASA Headquarters were pre-selected before the text was funneled up the pipeline to help facilitate a quick turnaround on text reviews.

As our fastest resource for disseminating information, social media would play an important role during the press release. For example, recent research has found that 54% of U.S. adults say they at least sometimes get news from social media (*Pew Research Center, 2024*). In addition to the release text, the writers were tasked with writing Facebook, Twitter (now X) and Instagram posts for each target. A Microsoft

Word template was created specifically for these posts so that the social media manager had all of the information necessary for scheduling the image posts.

Each platform required different texts and specific features in each platform were used to best amplify the post. For instance, Facebook allowed for a longer post and a direct link to the release. Writers could explain more about the image and release without requiring users to click the link to the full release for more information. Because of X's smaller character limit, the writers provided more of a teaser where the text enthusiastically encouraged users to click on the link to learn more about the image. Similarly, Instagram posts began with a teaser-like introduction before expanding on the images in more detail and also encouraged readers to click on the website link in the account's bio to learn more, as Instagram does not allow for hyperlinks from individual posts.

Overall, much of the release's success was due to several key tactics, including diligent preparation, organisation and planning, careful coordination and communication internally at STScI and externally with NASA and partners, and a spirit of trust and cooperation.

Website: Moving to the Cloud

As the science deep-dive site for *Webb*, the STScI-led [WebbTelescope.org](https://www.webbtelescope.org) is the repository for all full-resolution *Webb* images and graphics, and the ERO press release would direct the audience to this website for the full array of download options. As a result, it needed to be able to handle the traffic. It was thus important to know how much traffic should be expected – a major source of uncertainty.

Shortly after *Webb*'s launch, public reaction began to grow quickly, and it became evident that we might see unprecedented website traffic that would be better served by cloud-based infrastructure. The cloud infrastructure would allow us to utilise external resources to scale up infrastructure to meet the increased demands and subsequently scale back down as demand waned. Although we had taken steps in years before moving our press release image and video assets to the cloud, most of our website infrastructure remained on-premise. To ensure our web infrastructure would meet projected levels of traffic, STScI management, technical staff, and senior leadership made a series of quick and proactive decisions to clear the path to move the full web infrastructure to the cloud.

This was no small effort since this meant moving a suite of other websites from within the same technical ecosystem. Over the course of the next six months, the STScI team worked diligently both internally and with external contractors to plan, execute, and test the move to the cloud, including putting in place multiple fail-safes in case events did not go as planned, such as pre-flighting data on backup servers that could be manually put in place in the event of a server crash.

By July 2022, the team had completed all critical tasks, and the tests met our internal benchmarks for predicted traffic. The benchmarks we developed were estimates

derived from metrics acquired from NASA's "Where is *Webb*?" interactive, which the public had been using to track the progress of *Webb* on its journey to the Sun-Earth Lagrange Point 2. To test the performance and stability of our infrastructure against these benchmarks, we utilised open-source load testing tools to simulate high-volume user requests to our website, which far surpassed our targets. We felt confident and ready for the large amount of expected web traffic.

Accessibility: Sharing the Wonder

In alignment with STScI's overarching strategic goal of "making the world's astronomical information accessible to all" (*Space Telescope Science Institute [STScI], n.d.*), the Office of Public Outreach has undertaken a major, multi-year digital accessibility initiative, of which [WebbTelescope.org](https://www.webbtelescope.org) is a key beneficiary. The initiative, which started before *Webb*'s launch, has provided ongoing and dedicated resources toward enhancing inclusive access and interaction with our public-facing websites by adhering to a unified set of best practices rooted in Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0. AA compliance standards that focus on truly enhancing access to our websites for all users (*Tateo 2021*). This has included automated and manual full-site reviews with the help of outside accessibility consultants. As a result, almost every element of the site has been improved, ranging from contrast and text styling to video players and carousels to navigation and forms.

This effort has involved targeted improvements by STScI writers, designers, software engineers, content managers, scientists, and education specialists, as well as external accessibility experts and members of the blind and low-vision community, who also provided evaluation services and guidance for our efforts.

For the *Webb* early release observations, our team prioritised the highest impact, highest value work first to help enhance the experience for all users. The highlight of these efforts was overall improvements to the home page, press release pages, and multimedia pages since this was where much of the public focus would land. We emphasised removing elements that might

prevent users from carrying out tasks or drastically decrease their effectiveness when doing so, with a particular focus on ensuring content– and the methods to access that content– followed the four accessibility principles: they are perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust. We wanted to ensure every person could truly experience the technological achievement of the First Images to the best of their abilities.

Significant effort was made to develop and implement a process for writing and including image descriptions (alternative text, or alt text) on all ERO images, which would ultimately be embedded into the website's source code. This would make each image readable to anyone using assistive technologies to access [WebbTelescope.org](https://www.webbtelescope.org).

To ensure these descriptions met our needs, we initially started with the Cooper Hewitt Guidelines for Image Description (*Cooper Hewitt, n.d.*) but then developed an internal style guide suited to our particular needs. This was based on trial and error, including feedback from members of the blind and visually impaired community. Our internal guidelines included focusing on what the image looks like rather than what science it represents, being detailed and specific ("pointing in this direction," "stretching for one-third of the length of the image"), mentioning qualities like colour, and making analogies to objects people may be familiar with. Similar guidelines are used by the *Chandra X-ray Observatory* in their innovative accessibility efforts (*Arcand et al., 2023*).

Coordinating with Partners

Accessibility was not the only way we extended the reach of the First Images. Partners were critical in developing and operating the telescope and making it a public success.

All communications and engagement done by STScI on behalf of *Webb* EROs were coordinated with all three international agencies (NASA, ESA, CSA) and the main industry partner, Northrop Grumman. Subcontractors, including Honeywell, L3 Harris, and Ball Aerospace, were often also part of the planning conversations.

For the early release observations specifically, the plans were spearheaded by STScI, but partners were apprised of the process and schedule well ahead of time and were consulted, as appropriate, during the actual production process. For example, the exoplanet observations were taken using the instrument developed by the Canadian Space Agency, and they were consulted both in the creation of the spectra style and the final creation of the graphic to showcase the data.

Another important partnership developed with informal learning communities across the country and the globe. An extended engagement programme called the *Webb* Community Events Initiative began in the year leading up to the telescope's launch and continued through commissioning and First Images. This initiative, jointly led by STScI and NASA, leveraged the NASA Science Activation programme's extensive partners and networks to bring *Webb*'s engineering and science more directly into local communities. This approach shared similarities with initiatives like the IAU 100th anniversary celebration (González et al., 2020) and NASA's 2017 eclipse effort.

The Community Events Initiative supported several hundred host sites interested in celebrating *Webb*'s launch and First Images with their communities. Those sites included museums, science centres, libraries, camps, amateur astronomy clubs, and other community groups across the US. Participating sites were required to be non-profit organisations and were asked to host a free public event, work with local partners to reach new or underserved audiences, have a safety/COVID plan with a backup plan for a digital-only event, attend a training session on *Webb*'s mission and science, and participate in gathering outreach evaluation data. Sites were also strongly encouraged to involve a NASA, STScI, or other Subject Matter Expert (SME) in their event. All non-profit organisations agreeing to these terms were selected to participate.

Each host site was provided with a point of contact on the joint NASA/STScI Community Events Initiative team for one-on-one communication throughout their event planning. Support for host sites also included training on the *Webb* mission and its science, press and social media kits, a curated set of hands-on and digital activities, visuals and media, an outreach slide deck,

tips for hosting events, and access to print materials and handouts. The team connected over 250 launch event hosts with 186 *Webb* scientists and engineers. For the celebrations of *Webb*'s first images and spectra, the team provided access to virtual panels of scientists (in English and in Spanish) who talked about the science behind the targets of the First Images shortly after their release. An interactive community event map with filterable information was also created to support and showcase events hosted nationwide to celebrate *Webb*'s first images and spectra.

In a survey of host sites, 91% reported that the events were very effective in sharing the value of scientific discovery with images and other data that will inspire curiosity. The ability to connect directly with people through their local establishments and provide them with a personal connection to *Webb* arguably deepened the impact of the First Images release campaign.

Timing: A Staggering Plan

From the beginning of detailed planning in 2021, there was general agreement that *Webb*'s first images and data should be issued as a single news package to avoid favouring any instrument or science theme. This plan evolved in the three months leading up to the release when NASA opted to present a staggered release instead.

NASA planned a one-hour live broadcast to unveil the *Webb* images, one target at a time, to create an "Oscar-like buzz" and increase audience interest. This plan required switching from one "wrapper" release and a series of image captions to six separate releases (five targets plus one overarching release), along with all the other supporting materials. Fortunately, it was agreed that the release times would be fixed, and if the broadcast ran fast or slow, partners would not have to adjust their timing accordingly when publishing online.

A final challenge was thrown into the timing just a week before the release, when the White House decided to hold a media briefing² about *Webb* on 11 July, the day before the full release, so President Biden could unveil the first *Webb* image. This added a seventh release to the mix, focused solely on *Webb*'s First Deep Field,

which would publish online the night of the 11th in conjunction with the briefing. The impact was undeniable. STScI used a media tracking service to measure the number of impressions of this initial release, as well as the full package. Impressions measure how many times content appears on a user's screen. It is based on average monthly visitors to the websites in question. It is not a quantified headcount of individuals who viewed a specific webpage because that data is proprietary to news organisations. For the image unveiled by President Biden, media tracking showed 6.65 billion impressions by 14:30 UTC on Tuesday, 12 July.

Impact

On 12 July, the complete collection of *Webb*'s first images and data was shared with the world. The results arguably captured the attention of billions of people (Figure 4).

In conventional media, a tracking report one week after the release found 26,500 online articles – exceeding the number that could be downloaded from the Meltwater media tracking service used by STScI (26,000) – and a total of 117 billion impressions.

Between 11 and 17 July, the released images significantly impacted STScI's social media accounts. The institution's Facebook posts had 894,000 impressions, and Instagram posts reached more than 31,000 likes. However, the X account saw the most action, with more than 9,172,000 impressions in that timeframe.

Our deep-dive science website, WebbTelescope.org, witnessed over 28,000,000 page views across nearly 3,500,000 unique users during the same period. Additionally, the resulting virality of all of this effort meant that people were sharing *Webb*'s images around the globe through their own social media accounts, often linking directly to the source: high-resolution images that STScI was hosting on our Amazon Web Services (AWS) cloud servers. The resulting traffic, which inadvertently coincided with Amazon's largest online event of the year, Prime Day, resulted in over 400,000,000 individual requests and the transfer of over 500 terabytes (TB) of data.

Credit: STScI

Figure 4: A sample of front pages from newspapers worldwide that featured Webb's First Images. Image Credit: STScI

It also became clear that releasing the first images and spectra became an international cultural moment. On July 12, the Google Doodle, an animation of *Webb*, celebrated the special day. Cultural landmarks, including Times Square (*Times Square, 2022*) in New York City and Piccadilly Circus in London, had the images plastered across their giant digital billboards. The Empire State Building also lit up in yellow as an ode to *Webb's* gold mirrors.

On social media, many top brands, sports teams, astronauts, and celebrities were talking about *Webb* and sharing the First Images. Some notable mentions included actress Mia Farrow, singer Hank Green, actor William Shatner (Captain Kirk), and the Star Wars franchise. There were countless posts and memes created that circulated the internet for days after the release.

Several musical artists, including Coldplay and Jimmy Buffett, also incorporated *Webb's* images into their concert performances in the week following the ERO release. On 12 July, Brian May, famed guitarist of Queen, released a song inspired

by the observatory, "Floating in Heaven," whose accompanying music video featured the First Images. Both NASA and STScI helped to facilitate these musical celebrations.

Also, within weeks, websites carried merchandise sporting *Webb's* First Images. Now, people could buy a Carina Nebula sweatshirt or *Webb's* First Deep Field socks.

Even the team's accessibility efforts were noticed. Media outlets such as the Washington Post (*Vargas, 2022*) and NPR wrote stories specifically about *Webb's* alt text. The reaction in the Blind and low-vision community was also meaningful, as testimonials about the impact of this work began to spring up across social media (e.g., *Emery, 2022*). The rich, poetic image descriptions struck a chord with people across the world, many of whom had never fully been able to experience these images (e.g., *Mixtochtli, 2022*) but were now being offered a much more focused and detailed description of these observations.

Lessons Learned and Conclusions

Perhaps the most important factor in the success of *Webb's* first images and spectra was the ability of the STScI ERO production team to work independently and cohesively, with appropriate oversight. This was one of the most anticipated astronomical events of the decade. With so many partners involved and so many people who had spent years working on the mission, there were plenty of opinions to go around regarding the final news package. By working independently, without direct influence from NASA or other stakeholders, the ERO production team could serve as an unbiased third party with one overarching goal: to create the most impactful release package possible that showcased *Webb's* abilities across several areas of astronomy.

The daily production schedule was very helpful not only for internal coordination but also for keeping NASA and other stakeholders informed. Through regular updates, we were able to let NASA know when observations were successful and when they could expect materials for review. Reviewers were asked

to clear their schedules on days that text and graphics were due from STScI to ensure a quick turnaround.

Near-daily production meetings were key to sharing information and keeping the ERO production team informed and on course. Among other benefits, writers had a direct line of communication with internal subject matter experts and could get the details they needed to flesh out the release text. The flow of information and knowledge was two-directional, as scientists also had direct access to internal communication experts.

Finally, flexibility was key. The dedicated team understood that weekend and after-hours work would be necessary for a very focused period of time. They did what needed to be done because they understood the ultimate goal and knew that, in the end, it would all be very worthwhile.

These key factors – independence, a detailed schedule and regular production meetings, clear communication and coordination, and flexibility – can apply to similar challenges in the future, whether for space missions, ground-based observatories, or other high-profile events.

The sense of pride when *Webb*'s first images and spectra were unveiled was powerful. Our loftiest goal had been reached: the *Webb Space Telescope* became a household name overnight, joining *Hubble* as one of the most recognisable observatories in the world (or beyond) (*Launius & DeVorkin, 2014*).

Notes:

¹ *Webb*'s field of regard: <https://webbtelescope.org/contents/media/videos/1157-Video>

² President Biden and Vice President Harris receive a briefing on *James Webb Space Telescope* images: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ySalPoHisRg>

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Biographies

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